

Science for the 21st Century: Attacking Great Interdisciplinary Challenges

The Grand Challenge

The digital revolution offers profound opportunities for science to discover hitherto unsuspected patterns and relationships in nature and society, on scales from the molecular to the cosmic, from local health systems to global sustainability. It has created the potential for the disciplines of science to achieve more holistic understanding of the complexity that underlies the challenges that confront humanity, including most of the Sustainable Development Goals, by exposing their deep structure through the integration of data across relevant disciplines. However, a barrier to realisation and exploitation of this potential arises from the varying data standards and vocabularies that have been used across disciplines. Online Integration of diverse data from globally distributed sources can often only be achieved within and between closely allied fields. The problem has been tackled by many projects but with so much research time and effort spent reconciling disparate datasets, the challenge remains to make online data integration a routine, less-specialised aspect of data-driven science.

The Response: ICSU-CODATA Data Integration Initiative

The Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA) of the International Council for Science (ICSU) is launching a major programme to address this fundamental issue for science. This is likely to be the work of a decade, but with the potential to create a dramatic shift in the way that interdisciplinary science is done in the 21st century, and the impacts it achieves. The programme has two strands:

Strand 1: Pilot programmes in specific domains (initially: infectious disease; disaster risk; resilient cities; agriculture) that demonstrate the power and useable benefits of online data integration, and provide solutions to the current difficulties. This will lead to a generalisation of widely applicable methods.

Strand 2: Support for disciplines that have not yet developed the standards that are necessary for effective online data integration and real time programmatic access to data.

Why will the International Science Council (ISC) be a Key Player?

In July 2018, ICSU will merge with the International Social Science Council to create ISC, a body that will represent all the sciences, recognise and support the imperative for interdisciplinary research in addressing a vision of science for the 'global public good'. The data integration initiative is central to the new Council's priorities in promoting policies that assist science to adapt to and exploit the digital revolution. It will be uniquely positioned to do so by involving its members, both from the disciplinary unions and associations that represent the international dimension of the science disciplines, and from national members that are the interdisciplinary representatives of national priorities.

Actions

A community of interest and experience has been created in involving a wide range of scientific bodies acting or interested in the integration issue. Funding has been obtained to create definitive bids for the Strand 1 pilot projects by autumn 2018. With the support of ICSU & ISSC, CODATA is systematically approaching their unions and associations to engage them formally in a process designed to forge powerful tools for a new era of interdisciplinary science. For more information, contact Simon Hodson, CODATA Executive Director, at: dataintegration@codata.org.